

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF READING LITERACY IN THE STUDENTS OF THE PREPARATORY GROUP OF SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: In this article, in recent years, preschool education organizations have decided on the development of children, as well as pre-school preparation groups in the development of children's reading literacy. information is provided.

Keywords: Attitude, empathy, benevolence, talkativeness, naturalness, organization, openness, feelings, confrontation, attention, thinking, perception, imagination, memory, as well as reading, writing, interactive learning.

In the world, it is necessary to introduce modern forms of high-quality preschool education in order to increase the child's opportunities for primary education. In countries such as South Korea, England, the USA, Japan, Russia and Germany, great attention is paid to the use of innovative educational technologies to prepare preschool children for school education and to form an interest in knowledge, to develop children's reading literacy based on a competence approach. In particular, the creation of an environment that encourages the preparation of 5-7-year-old children for school education and the development and implementation of innovative technologies for the effective organization of learning and learning activities, the popularization of foreign experiences in this regard is of urgent importance. In our country, the state policy in the field of development of preschool education has been developed, on the basis of increasing the scope of coverage of children with quality preschool education, intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children, introduction of innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the process of preschool education and upbringing, large-scale reforms are underway to create and introduce mechanisms for assessing children's development and readiness for general primary education. In particular, in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, which was developed based on the principle of "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development", the level of coverage in preschool education should be increased to 80%, the quality of education in the preschool education system should be brought to a new level, scientific-based approaches to the processes of preschool education on the basis of which the goals of the priority areas of improvement ¹were determined. In the course of these reforms, it is important to create educational programs aimed at preparing older preschool children for school education in accordance with the state standards of preschool education and upbringing, including improving the technologies of developing children's reading literacy based on a

¹ Uzbekistan Republic of the President of January 28 , 2022 " For 2022 - 2026 intended New of Uzbekistan development strategy about " gi Decree No. PF-60 .

competence approach.

During the trial period, special importance was attached to communication in the development of reading literacy in preschool children. In the process of communication, children interacted with each other in intellectual and work activities. Communication served as the primary means of directing children toward goals. In some situations, there were misunderstandings in the exchange of information, for example, when a child wanted to talk with a peer in a certain direction, that is, he wanted to tell about a cartoon or a fairy tale that he saw at home yesterday, the second child began to express his feelings about the game he played, in this case, mutual misunderstanding was observed. In this process, the teacher-educator instructed the children to exchange, understand and understand various information. In addition, children were guided to interact with each other in the process of communication and experience the process together.

During the experiment, children were given an understanding of the main tasks of communication, that is, *information transfer; engage in interactive conversation; mutual understanding; arousing expressive-emotional feelings*.

Naturally, the formation of a child's personality is impossible without communication, communication becomes a primary need in any activity. Communication is the key to any person's success. It is known that communication takes place in verbal and non-verbal forms. "There are different reasons for the need to use gestures in speech, and additional paralinguistic tools - gestures and facial expressions are needed in communication . " In this sense ², signs and symbols, gestures, facial expressions were effectively used along with verbal communication in the development of reading literacy in children of preschool age . It is known that speech, which is a clear external expression of language, is a connecting chain of social activity. In this sense, children have the ability to understand the essence of existing concepts, to know words, to master language tools and, most importantly, to enter into communication correctly and easily.

The development of speech activity of older preschool children was carried out in several successive stages: *orientation, planning, implementation, control or influence*. The children were taught to follow the culture of greeting when delivering their speech, coherence of the spoken words, prompting the interlocutor to action, answering questions, talking on a mobile phone. The speech situation is manifested in the rules for the correct conduct of the conversation and the expression of speech, for example, children use different forms of speech in conversations with their teachers and peers.

Speech acts are carried out in the following stages:

- 1) preparation, that is, understanding of goals and motives;
- 2) diagnosis of needs and results is carried out;
- 3) expression of thought (choice of words and correct expression);
- 4) the transformation of internal speech into external speech.

Understanding speech requires understanding its content. The content of spoken communication consists of sender(s) and receiver(s) of information. The formation of the following qualities for communication in children was achieved:

- empathy - imagining the whole world through other people's eyes, understanding others;
- benevolence - not only the ability to feel, but also to show one's friendly attitude, to treat other people with respect;

²Nurmonov A. Selected works. Three volumes. - T.: Akademnashr, 2012. Volume 1. - B. 182.

- by approving the actions of the interlocutor , the ability to understand was formed in them;
- support of peers and others;
- naturalness - aspiration, showing oneself as one is, not "wearing a mask" or playing a role;
- refusing general discussions, talking about current reality and events, answering questions at the same time;
- organization - propensity for activity, establishing communication with personal initiative; to speak and communicate directly;

openness - showing one's inner world to others, self-confidence, establishing strong relations with others;

accepting emotions , understanding the emotional states of the interlocutor-partner;

- to be ready for conflicting situations, to establish a reliable relationship with the interlocutor.

In the development of reading literacy in older preschool children, emphasis was placed on forming the desire to interact with people around them, the ability to organize communication, and the ability to understand the interlocutor. Children were guided to understand the feelings of the interlocutor, to show a positive or negative attitude towards him , to eliminate conflict situations and to use their speech correctly. Instructions were given on knowing the rules and standards of communication , their use and compliance during communication. The components of development of reading literacy in children of preschool age , criteria and indicators for their determination were formed taking into account age characteristics.

Oral, visual, and practical methods were used individually and in a mixed way depending on the pedagogical situation to study the development of children's reading literacy during the experimental period . Based on the "First Step" educational program, didactic games were developed for 6-7-year-old children that develop speech and communication skills . In these games, verbal, visual and practical methods were used in a complex manner.

Literacy training of children is carried out in preparatory groups of mass preschool education organizations, in short-term groups, in preschool educational institutions established on the basis of existing private and public-private partnerships, where preschool preparatory groups exist. they enter.

1. Reading skill by:

- 1) reads the word by heart;
- 2) the word reads in syllables;
- 3) knows all the letters and them shot
- 4) the words to joints will be
- 5) flash cards using from joints words creates ;
- 6) word , sound syllable , sentence about to understanding have
- 7) of the word lexical , syllabic and phonetic structure about to the imagination have will be
- 8) peshlavha , book names , pictures at the bottom records reads ;
- 9) speech hears and understands .

2. Writing skills:

- 1) writes straight lines, words and short sentences on paper;

- 2) in the notebook writing lines determine takes
- 3) pictures right places ;
- 4) everyone knows how to write a letter in printed form ;
- 5) the hand without disconnecting point lines by combining picture draws

3. Readiness to analyze sound :

- 1) s divides itself into syllables;
- 2) separates the sound in a word or syllable;
- 3) all pronounce the sound correctly;
- 4) focuses on the high or low speech, diction.

4. Verbal connected speech :

- 1) his mother tongue free they speak ;
- 2) different sentences creates ;
- 3) builds a visual story based on personal experience independently;
- 4) narrates artistic works of various genres expressively;
- 5) rhymes creates ;
- 6) riddles finds ;
- 7) in his speech foreign the words applies ;
- 8) small poems from memory says ;
- 9) tells other children the content of the book he remembers;
- 10) different meaning forms independent respectively make up and speaking to give knows

As can be seen from the above, teaching literacy is a very responsible process, and it is necessary to ensure that the lessons are organized using educational games, interactive methods and ICT that ensure active participation of children.

SUMMARY AND SPECIFICATIONS:

In conclusion, it is worth noting that reading literacy ensures the development of the child's mental abilities, such as the mental processes of knowledge: attention, thinking, perception, imagination, memory, as well as enriching the skills and abilities of reading, writing , with the help of games in a natural form suitable for educational requirements.

In order to develop creative abilities of preschool children, interesting didactic games, logical exercises, puzzles, and tasks that develop logical thinking are effective.

Interactive education - develops students' communication skills and abilities, helps to establish emotional relationships between them, teaches them to work in a team, listen to the opinions of their peers, and ensures the fulfillment of educational tasks by teaching them to think independently.

Human literacy determines the level of the quality of his future life and makes it possible to successfully operate in the period of rapid technical development of today's world. Thus, to be literate means to have the key to knowledge.

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